

FigS2. Boxplot overview of the upshift experiments on all the strains.

These graphs show the spread by a boxplot of the single cells for every time point in the experiment. The bottom and the top of the box represent respectively the 25th and of 75th percentile and the middle band in the box represent the 50th percentile or median. The upper and the lower whisker represent a maximum of 1.5 IQR. The dots represent outliers. Each graph corresponds to one upshift experiments. The different strains are displayed vertically and the different concentrations are displayed horizontally. The wild-type strain displays the lowest spread of the measurements.